

CONNECTING GRAPHICAL SCORES TO SOUND SYNTHESIS IN PWGL

Mika Kuuskankare
Centre for Music and Technology
Sibelius Academy
Helsinki, Finland
mkuuskan@siba.fi

Mikael Laurson
Department of Signal Processing and Acoustics
Aalto University
Espoo, Finland
laurson@siba.fi

ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe how graphical scores can be coupled with synthesis algorithms in the visual programming language PWGL. The present approach is based on an extensible music notation and a direct connection to a flexible sound synthesis engine. We implement, as an exercise, a simple working model that makes it possible create graphical scores out of user defined graphical objects and connect the graphical objects to specific synthesis methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Creating a computer-based, extensible music notation system that can be tied directly to sound synthesis is a long-standing problem in the field of computer music. The integration between the two major tools, ENP [1] and PWGLSynth [2], inside the visual programming environment PWGL [3], is a step to this direction. There exists a long tradition of tools that explore the possibilities of combining graphics to sound synthesis. Lindemann's Animal [4] and Buxton's SSSP [5] were among the first experiments. A more up-to-date graphical score editor implementation can be found inside Pd as described by Puckette [6]. The UPIC [7] system developed by Iannis Xenakis in the mid 70's is perhaps the most notable example in this category and there have been several attempts, such as the open source IanniX [8], to recreate it using commodity hardware. However, most of these attempts concentrate solely on graphical notation.

The approach presented here makes no difference between a traditionally notated score and a graphical one. For example, the two ENP scores shown in Figure 1 both share the same underlying representation and they can both be created, manipulated, and performed in the same way. Up to now, our attempts of realizing performance models for ENP have been concentrated on controlling virtual instruments and more traditional sound sources, such as MIDI and sample libraries.

In this paper, we aim to demonstrate that it is relatively easy to extend PWGL so that it makes it possible also

to realize graphical scores. We show how to implement a PWGL playback device that can be used to play, through PWGLSynth, graphical scores prepared with the help of ENP. We describe the protocol that can be used to create new graphical symbols, demonstrate how to define the specific synthesis algorithms and how to create the connection between the two.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. First, we give a concise introduction to the playback scheme of PWGL and build a minimal playback device. Next, we discuss how to define visual synthesis instruments and collections thereof, i.e., orchestras. Then, we show how to create customized graphical objects and demonstrate how to control the aspects of visualization and synthesis through the use of properties. Finally, we put it all together by creating the connection between our synthesis instruments and the graphical objects. The paper ends with some concluding remarks.

2. THE IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 6 in the Appendix shows our target score lasting for about 20 seconds containing some user designed graphical objects. The score can be edited with the mouse and objects can be added, deleted, copied, and pasted using keyboard shortcuts. The vertical positioning, size and the duration of the objects can be edited by mouse drags. Other aspects can be controlled by using user-definable properties. The benefits and efficiency of using properties has already been reported by Dannenberg (see, for example [9]). Properties are name/value pairs and they can be manipulated either manually (through the ENP GUI) or algorithmically. In our case, the resulting sound can depend on or be defined by the graphical attributes. Conversely, the appearance of the graphical objects can be generated according to the synthesis properties.

The example score contains two kinds of objects: (1) a streaming sound sample player object that displays the sample data contained in a file named by the `filename` property, and (2) a sine-bank object that reads its frequency information from a sound analysis database and interpolates between two sets of frequencies. The frequency information retrieved from the analysis is stored by the synthesis algorithm as a property. The data which, in turn, is used when drawing the object.

Figure 1. (a) a graphical score, and (b) a traditionally notated score both prepared with the help of ENP. These scores share the same underlying object representation and hierarchy.

2.1 The Playback Device

PWGL Playback Devices are used to generate performance data (e.g. MIDI) for playback of ENP scores. A new playback device can be created by subclassing the abstract *pwgl-playback-device* class and specializing the pertinent methods. The performance data, in turn, is generated by calling a set of methods in a pre-defined order. Figure 2 shows the primary methods and their order of execution. As a general rule, the *prepare-playback* is used to initialize the player, e.g., by loading a sample database or preparing a specific instrument setup. *add-playback-note-event* method inserts each note found in the score into an event queue. *setup-playback* method, in turn, can be used to send arbitrary messages, such as, volume or pitch-bend information before the playback starts. Finally, during the realtime playback, *send-playback-event* is called for each event found in the event queue.

Figure 2. The pertinent PWGL playback methods and their order of execution.

Listing 1 shows the implementation of the PWGL playback device that can be used to play graphical scores.

We begin to implement our playback device by subclassing the *pwgl-onset-playback-device* class (a) which is specialized for sound sources that transmit only one playback event per note (as opposed to *pwgl-onset-offset-playback-device* which implements a control protocol, that applies

Listing 1 The definition of the PWGL playback device.

```

(a) (defclass GS-player (pwgl-onset-play-device) ())
(b) (defmethod prepare-playback* ((self GS-player) score)
(c)   (register-GS-instruments)
(d)   (compile-GS-expressions score)
(e)   (start/stop-GS-player))
(f) (defmethod send-playback-event ((output GS-player)
(g)   midi-info &optional vel?)
(h)   (dolist (expression (expressions note))
(i)     (funcall (read-key expression :rt-event-fn))))
  
```

among others to MIDI, where the onset of a note and the offset of the same note are considered as two separate events). In our case, this is sufficient, as the duration of an event can be controlled, for example, with an amplitude envelope.

Next, *prepare-playback** (b-e) registers all the available synthesis instruments, generates the playback code for the score objects (see *compile-GS-expressions* in line d) and caches the information for efficiency (see Section 2.3). Also, depending on the state of the synthesizer, it either starts or stops the playback process.

Finally, we need to specify how the actual playback event is sent to the output device (PWGLSynth in this case). The synthesis events have been compiled as function calls by the *compile-GS-expressions* method. Thus, *send-playback-event* (f-i) simply executes the cached functions one at the time (see line i).

2.2 Defining the Graphical Objects

Next, we create our custom ENP-expressions[10] and define their visual appearance using the built-in expression editor, the ENP Expression Designer (ED, [11]). For our experimental player we need two kinds of graphical objects: one that represents sound samples, and another that represents a sine bank with two sets of sine waves.

Figure 3 gives, as an example, the complete ED session that is used to define the sound sample expression. As our system is object-oriented we define a new ENP-expression class through inheritance. In this case the class name, *sample*, is given at the top left part of the editor. This class identity is of primary importance as it is later used to tie

together the graphical object created here and the methods that generate the actual synthesis information.

The visual representation is defined at the upper part of the editor using the combination of Lisp and a set of pre-defined OpenGL macros. Here, we first draw a rectangle (*draw-2D-box*) whose y dimension is chosen arbitrarily and the x dimension corresponds to the duration of the sample. In addition, we draw the value of the *:filename* property above the rectangle, and finally, a built-in function *draw-sound-object* is used to draw the sample data inside the enclosing rectangle. A preview of the expression is displayed at the lower part of the editor.

Figure 3. ENP expression designer can be used to define the objects needed for realizing a graphical score. Here, an object visually representing a sound sample is realized.

To save some space, for our second object we give only the code that defines its appearance (see Listing 2). Here, we assume that the two properties *:freqs1* and *:freqs2* each contain a list of frequencies. The two lists of frequencies are pre-calculated by the part of our scheme that generates the corresponding synthesis algorithm. The meaning of these lists is explained in Section 2.3. At this point, it suffices to know that the graphical output should reflect that fact that the synthesis algorithm interpolates between the two frequency sets so that the frequencies defined by *:freqs1* gradually fade out and, conversely, the frequencies defined by *:freqs2* fade in. The code is again relatively straightforward. Lines a-b access the frequency properties. Lines c-d retrieve the upper and lower bounds of the whole frequency envelope. The remaining parts of the code consist of two almost identical sections, lines f-i and j-m, that draw the appropriate frequency sets using colors that fade in and out accordingly. Finally, in (n) we enclose the object inside a rectangle.

As can be seen it is relatively easy to define a new graphical object in ENP. The process is interactive and the results are immediately usable. The graphical output

Listing 2 The drawing code of the sine-bank object.

```
(a) (let ((freqs1 (get-enp-property expression :freqs1))
        (freqs2 (get-enp-property expression :freqs2)))
    (c) (let ((maxf (max (apply #'max freqs1) (apply #'max freqs2)))
            (minf (min (apply #'min freqs1) (apply #'min freqs2))))
        (e) (with-gl-line-width 0.5
            (f) (with-2D-object :lines
                (g) (dolist (freq (pw::g-scaling freqs1 -1.0 1.0 minf maxf))
                    (h) (with-gl-color :white (add-2d-vertex 0.0 freq))
                    (i) (with-gl-color :black (add-2d-vertex width freq))))
                (j) (with-2D-object :lines
                    (k) (dolist (freq (pw::g-scaling freqs2 -1.0 1.0 minf maxf))
                        (l) (with-gl-color :black (add-2d-vertex 0.0 freq))
                        (m) (with-gl-color :white (add-2d-vertex width freq))))))
            (n) (with-gl-color :gray (draw-2d-box 0.0 -1.1 width 1.1))
```

can be changed at any time and the changes are dynamically propagated across all the instances of the object in question.

2.3 Defining the Synthesis Algorithms

Figure 4 shows the visual instrument definition of our sample player. The connection between the visual instrument definition shown here and the specific synthesis algorithm is based on the boxes named *synth-plug*. These boxes define control entry points for our instrument. The ones labelled “D” (as in discrete) allow us to update values. The synth-plug boxes labelled “T”, in turn, are used as triggers. All synth-plug boxes have as their first input the name of the control parameter (e.g. *:amp*, *:trig*, etc.). These symbolic references allow the user to refer to specific inputs while sending control events to the instrument.

In our visual instrument definition, the lines a, c, and e are of most importance (cf. Section 2.4). The *:set-env* and *:trig-env* (a) are used to store the incoming envelope data and trigger it respectively. The two entry points in (c) are used to control the built-in sample-player box (d). *:id* is used to select the sample from the internal sample database and *:trig* is used to trigger the sample player to start playing.

Furthermore, since we are talking about a multi-timbral player, we also need to define a patch that acts as our orchestra definition. As shown in Figure 5 the orchestra patch contains both instruments (*sine-bank* and *sampler*) and connects them to a PWGLSynth player box. The abstraction box containing the sound sample player, the implementation of which is shown in Figure 4, is labeled “Sampler”, and can be seen at the top right corner of the patch.

2.4 Connecting the Graphics to Sound Synthesis

So far, we have defined a collection of new ENP-expressions and synthesis instruments. Next, we need to create the connection between the two. To accomplish our task we take an advantage of a newly created *RT-events* syntax [12] which can be used to express control information using Lisp forms. This syntax allows us to write Lisp expressions which, in turn, can be used to control low-level synthesis parameters of our synthesizer, e.g., to trigger events and write control values to specific inputs. The connection between the graphical objects and the visual instrument definition is implemented so that for every

Figure 4. A PWGL patch showing the implementation of a simple sample player.

Figure 5. The “synth orchestra” patch containing two synth instruments *sine-bank* and *sampler*.

ENP-expression we provide a method called *expression-2-RT-events* which generates control information in the RT-events format. Furthermore, these methods can read from and write to the associated graphical objects any freely chosen property. Thus, the information generated here can be used to control some visual aspects. Also, the properties defined by the user or by the graphical object (such as duration or pitch) can, in turn, be used as a variable in the control data calculation.

Let us next examine the *expression-2-RT-events* method written for the sample player object in more detail. As explained, the functionality of this object depends on the *:filename* property. We used it in our visualization code to access the correct sample data for drawing. We also needed the property in our visual instrument definition as an argument to one of the synth-plugin boxes (*:id*).

In Listing 3 we connect the graphical object to the visual instrument definition shown in Figure 4 by implementing the corresponding *expression-2-RT-events* method. The *:filename* property is accessed in our code in (b). The next lines do various checks (e.g., if the sample exists) and initializations, such as loading the sample by demand and accessing the numeric sample id required by the sample-player. Note, that due to the deliberate use Lisp backquote syntax, the samples are loaded when the playback data is generated and cached and not during realtime playback. In lines c-d the combination of the synth-event *:set-env* and the synth-trigger *:trig-env* is used to store and make active the amplitude envelope information using the appropriate entry points found in our visual instrument definition (see (a) in Figure 4). Finally, (e) – (f) are used to set the appropriate sample id (*:id*) and to trigger the sample-player box to render the sound (*:trig*). Thus, the implementation is now complete.

Listing 3 The RT-events code implementing the discrete and continuous control events used to drive our visual instrument defined in Figure 4.

```
(a) (defmethod expression-2-RT-events ((self sample))
(b)   (when-let (filename (get-enp-property self :filename))
(c)     (let ((sample (sample-object-exists-p filename)))
(d)       (unless sample
(e)         (setq sample (load-sound-sample (namestring filename)))
(f)         (let* ((dur (duration sample))
(g)             (id (sampleID sample)))
(h)           `(with-synth-instrument ,(GS-player-instrument :sampler) 1
(i)             (synth-event 0.0 :set-env ',(make-envelope '((0.0 0.3)
(j)                 (0.98 0.3)
(k)                 (1.0 0.0))
(l)                 "amp env"
(m)                 dur)
(n)               :id 1 :namespace :sampler)
(o)             (synth-trigger 0.0 :trig-env :id 1 :namespace :sampler)
(p)             (synth-event 0.0 :id ,id :id 1 :namespace :sampler)
(q)             (synth-trigger 0.0 :trig :id 1 :namespace :sampler))))))
```

3. DISCUSSION

Using the concepts presented here it would be relatively straightforward to implement, for example, a simple but working multi-channel sample player à la ProTools. As an extension we could display the amplitude envelope or panning as an overlay to the sample objects. Several ENP-expressions are already able to display break-point functions as a part of the musical texture. Therefore, it would

be relatively easy to implement this feature as we could incorporate the envelope functionality, including display and editability, through inheritance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we describe how graphical scores can be coupled with arbitrary synthesis algorithms in the visual programming language PWGL. We demonstrate how to implement a PWGL playback device that can be used to play a graphical score. We use the built-in editor to create graphical objects that can represent arbitrary complex synthesis algorithms (e.g., sound samples and resonator banks). We also demonstrate how to use user definable properties to control aspects of both sound and graphical objects. The main contribution of this paper is to show how an extensible music notation system can be connected to a flexible sound synthesis engine.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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6. REFERENCES

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A. APPENDIX

Figure 6. A graphical score realized with the help of ENP. The objects shown here are user definable and can depend on or be defined by editable properties or synthesis algorithms connected to them.